

FORMS OF LEGAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND LEGAL CULTURE, STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article is about legal consciousness and legal culture development of its legal basis, especially citizens in society aimed at forming the legal knowledge and skills of the young generation about things. In addition, forms of legal consciousness and legal culture, Their tasks are mentioned. Citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan practical measures aimed at increasing legal awareness and culture cited.

Key words: law, legal consciousness, legal culture, community benefit, idea, legal education, law.

Legal culture is based on the age-old traditions, customs, language, religion of our people. Honesty and faith, justice and legality, based on the spirit, are superior to man Enlightenment and truth feelings such as respect and attention, patience serves to absorb. That's why people's thoughts and worldview a legal culture focused on selfless work for our independence promotion is a vital necessity. Legal culture and legal awareness of the population improvement, legal education and enlightenment, the order of legal knowledge in society improvement, based on deep respect and respect for human rights and freedoms attitude, people's sense of obedience to the law, knowledge of laws and to him Deciding on the happiness of strict adherence is a necessary requirement of today is coming In the process of building a legal democratic state and a just civil society, first of all, forming the legal consciousness and legal culture of every citizen is the main and important task. Establishment of legal democratic state and civil society in our country large-scale reforms are being carried out in terms of formation. Including PF-5618 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 No. "The system of raising legal consciousness and legal culture in society the decree on fundamental improvement" was adopted. Legal population increase the efficiency of work on raising awareness and legal culture improvement, in harmony with the social and political changes of citizens introducing modern methods of improving legal knowledge, as well as protecting the population, especially young people, from harmful information in order to form strong legal immunity for:

1. The following are legal consciousness and legal culture in society The main tasks of promotion were defined as: socio-economic to the population implemented in our

country content of reforms, adopted legislation and state programs and the formation of a system of consistent delivery of the essence, citizens in his mind, "Creating the spirit of respect for laws in society is the guarantee of building a democratic legal state!" life idea strengthening; in raising legal consciousness and legal culture in the society, eng First of all, it is important to conduct education in a systematic and organic manner attention, starting with the preschool education system, all of the population deep instilling of legal consciousness and legal culture into the layers, personal maintaining a balance between interests and the interests of society widely promote their ideas; concepts of right and duty, honesty and purity in the minds of the young generation and deeply inculcating the norms of etiquette go, teach them the important aspects of the Constitution from childhood; legal educational activities on the formation of legal culture among the population with the teaching of the history, religion, and national values of our people harmonious organization, as well as with state symbols on every citizen belonging to the country by forming feelings of pride, to strengthen the feeling of patriotism; legal consciousness and legal culture of civil servants promotion, corruption and other offenses in them forming an attitude of intolerance; state power and management bodies, including law addresses of protective bodies and institutions of civil society mutual cooperation in the implementation of legal propaganda strengthening; measures to increase legal awareness and legal culture in society wide and productive use of the principles of social partnership in organization set up on a systematic basis; in the provision of legal information by mass media increasing the role, wide use of innovative methods of legal advocacy, including expanding the use of web technologies; improvement of legal education, as well as legal personnel the system of training, retraining and improving their qualifications development; scientific of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society in-depth study of the basics.

2. "High legal culture is the development of the country Based on the conceptual idea of "guarantee", all layers of the population are legal achieve literacy, have a high level of legal awareness and systematic and organization of comprehensive legal promotion events state bodies and should be defined as one of the priority tasks of organizations.

In conclusion, it can be said that "Respect for laws in society "Resolving the spirit is the guarantee of building a democratic legal state!" Therefore, for the effective functioning of the laws, the citizens' legal it is very important to raise consciousness, legal culture, and legal ideology. The level of legal knowledge of all sections of the population, especially the younger generation by raising to a higher level we mean violations of the law, injustices, we will have prevented crimes. After all, every

citizen is economic and political service wherever they work in the current era of rapid reforms whether he does or does not study, he is bound to feel the need for legal knowledge at every step.

References

1. Saidov A. Tajinonov U. Theory of law. T. Justice. 2001 Page 22.
2. Saidov A. Tajinonov U. Theory of law. T. Justice. 2001, p. 35.
3. No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Presidential decree on the strategy of actions for development,
Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 6
4. Law No. PF-5618 dated January 9, 2019 "Legal consciousness and legal awareness in society
on the fundamental improvement of the culture promotion system" of the President Decree, National Database of Legal Documents, 10.01.2019, 06/19/5618/2452-number